

FATIGUE LIMIT: IS THERE A LINK TO THE QUASI-STATIC DAMAGE?

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents experimentally and numerically observed relations of the fatigue life limit and the quasi-static damage threshold, which provide rough estimation for the design strains to use under fatigue strength requirements and allow planning of the fatigue testing programs to minimize the amount of costly and time-consuming experiments with low loads and high number of cycles.

Keywords: Textile composites, short fibre composites, fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

“Fatigue limit” designates a load value below which the fatigue damage will never happen, or will happen with a very low probability. Practically this definition does not have a great value for composite materials, for which accelerated fatigue tests are not possible because the temperature increase for the polymer matrix places a limit for the test frequency. With the frequency range of 2÷10 Hz, stipulated by the standards, a test till 10^6 cycles lasts 6÷28 h, while test till 10^7 cycles lasts 60÷280 h, which makes the fatigue testing for determination of the fatigue limit a very challenging endeavor. Therefore, a “fatigue limit” is most often redefined to represent a load value below which the fatigue failure at a given (large) number of cycles does not happen. The number of cycles in question is selected based on a compromise between the requirements of the application and practical limitations of the test program. The most often used value is 10^6 cycles (“operational definition”) [1] – “1M” fatigue limit.

Talking about the fatigue limit in textile and short fibre composites, we restrict ourselves to the case of tension-tension fatigue with a constant (applied load) R-ratio of 0.1. We do not have enough experimental data for more complex loading cases to be able to formulate hypotheses and exhaustive conclusions. We also limit the loading conditions considering only the “fibre direction” of a textile composite. This term will be used to designate the direction of the tension (the direction along the tensile specimen), which coincide with the direction of one of the fibre (yarn) systems of the textile reinforcement.

In relation to the fatigue limit of cross-ply and multidirectional laminates, Talreja [1] makes a note, which is very relevant to the question asked in the title:

“Where is the fatigue limit? ... To determine the fatigue limit, if not available from the test data, a good estimate will be given by the strain at which transverse cracking initiates. The reasoning is simply

that if no cracks initiate in the transverse plies, no progression of crack multiplication and subsequent damage is possible”

From a practical point of view such estimation is extremely valuable, as it allows finding the fatigue limit without exhausting and costly test programs, or at least design such a program in an economical way, without wasting the resources in narrowing the search range. The paper challenges this idea for textile and short fibre composites through experimental and numerical studies respectively.

2 TEXTILE COMPOSITES

The behavior of textile composites proved to be more complex than the hypothesis in [1] mentioned in the previous section.

The sequence of damage events suggests a presence of two thresholds of the applied load. The first, designated as ϵ_1 , corresponds to the onset of the transverse cracking, which may not at this stage span the whole width of the specimen, being limited by the yarn crimp and/or presence of stitching in the textile reinforcement structure. The second, designated as ϵ_2 , corresponds to, on one hand, the onset of local delaminations and, on the other hand, to the formation of “strong” transverse cracks, which span the width of the specimen.

Figure 1: Relation of the 1M fatigue life limit strain and damage thresholds for different textile composites.

Previous works [2-14] have created a dataset, describing quasi-static and tension-tension fatigue behavior of various glass and carbon fiber reinforced thermoset textile composites. The dataset spans woven (2D and 3D), multiaxial warp knitted and braided reinforcements. For all the materials the damage thresholds in quasi-static tension, determined by AE analysis and confirmed by direct observation in stopped tests, were compared with tension-tension ($R = 0.1$) fatigue life limits, corresponding to the maximum strain in the first loading cycle giving the fatigue life of one million cycles.

Figure 1 summarizes the comparison between the fatigue life limit and the quasi-static damage thresholds under quasi-static loading (first loading cycle in fatigue): ε_1 represents initiation of matrix cracking in the transverse yarn system in the textile structure and ε_2 represents local delaminations on the scale of the reinforcement unit cell and development of “strong” transverse cracks, which span the width of the specimen. Diagrams show the ratio $\varepsilon_{1M_FL}/\varepsilon_1$ (for glass fiber reinforced composite) and $\varepsilon_{1M_FL}/\varepsilon_2$ (for carbon fiber reinforcements) for all the materials in the presented dataset.

For glass reinforced materials the 1M fatigue life limit is close to the quasi-static damage threshold ε_1 . The notable fact is that at the loads below the fatigue life limit, when the sample does not fail after several millions of fatigue cycles, the transverse matrix crack cracking still appear after certain number of cycles because of the matrix fatigue.

For carbon reinforced materials the ε_1 damage threshold is a serious underestimation of the fatigue life limit. The ε_2 threshold serves better as a conservative estimation of the 1M fatigue life limit. The underestimation can be as high as three times, depending on the material (see points corresponding to the carbon twill woven composites in Figure 1), but for some materials the strain of the 1M fatigue life limit is very close to the ε_2 threshold.

3 SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES

In this section, we check whether it is feasible to extend the note by Talreja [1] (mentioned in Section 1) to short fibre composites. In other words, the relation between the experimentally observed fatigue limit and damage initiation threshold in short fibre composites is evaluated using numerical methods.

Unlike textile composites, where the first damage event during cyclic loading is transverse cracking, short fibre composites suffer from fibre matrix debonding. It has been noted by several researchers [15]. As for textile composites, we limit ourselves exclusively to uni-axial tension tension loading. Though loading is not only in the “primary” fibre direction. Off-axis coupons with primary fibre directions 0° , 45° and 90° are also considered.

0° , 45° and 90° coupons were machined from injection molded plates made of Polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) reinforced with 50% wt. glass fibre. Fatigue tests were performed using a hydraulic horizontal Schenck fatigue testing machine. The applied loads had an R-ratio of 0.1 (ratio of minimum to maximum applied load). The fatigue limit of the three types of coupons was found to be 60, 33 and 20 MPa respectively. The value of the fatigue limit expectedly reduces as the primary fibre orientation direction (relative to loading) increases. The test methods including the SN curve have been previously published [16].

Once, the values of the fatigue limit have been experimentally determined, the next step is to calculate the onset of debonding (damage initiation threshold) via established numerical methods. We used the full Mori-Tanaka formulation for the homogenization of the short fibre composites. The full Mori-Tanaka formulation is known to have superior predictive abilities for stresses in individual fibres [17, 18]. Stresses in individual fibres are needed to model the onset of fibre matrix debonding. It must be noted that the Mori-Tanaka formulation is based on the mean field assumption, neglecting the stress

concentrations resulting from two (or more) fibres in close proximity to each other. The stress value predicted by the Mori-Tanaka formulation (which is subsequently used for calculating the damage initiation threshold) is the average value of stresses in fibres. Thus, the predicted value of the stress at damage initiation can be viewed as “upper bound”. In reality, the onset of damage due to stress concentrations will occur at a much lower value of stress.

The onset of damage is calculated from the average stresses in the fibre by first determining the stresses in the interphase by using displacement and traction continuity conditions at the interphase. Subsequently, the Modified Coulomb criterion, which combines the effect of normal and shear stress, is used to calculate the onset of fibre matrix debonding. Detailed description of the Modified coulomb criteria and extraction of the stresses at the interphase can be found in [19, 20].

It was seen that the predicted onset of debonding is significantly lower than the observed values (Figure 2). This despite the fact that average stresses in the fibre were used for the calculations, if stress concentrations were somehow incorporated into the calculations, the predicted values of onset of debonding can be expected to be even lower. Also, it can be confirmed that the damage initiation threshold shows no particular dependence on the primary orientation of the coupon. This is unlike the experimental observed trend where the fatigue limit decreased as a function of the primary fibre orientation direction.

We can thus say with reasonable confidence that the stress levels at the onset of debonding (first damage event in short fibre composites) have no correlation with fatigue limit. There is more than one damage event at the stresses leading to the fatigue limit of such materials.

Figure 2: Variation of the stress at which damage initiation occurs for 50% wt. GF reinforced PBT for coupons with different primary fibre orientation (relative to loading). Dashed lines indicate the measured range of stress to failure after 10^6 cycles. Arrow indicates the expected trend for stress to failure after 10^6 cycles for coupons machined in different directions with respect to the flow of the matrix.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of textile and short fibre composites proved to be more complex than a simple hypothesis proposed in [1] “a good estimate [of the fatigue limit] will be given by the strain at which transverse cracking initiates”.

This statement was observed to be reasonable for textile glass reinforced composites. For carbon reinforced materials the 1M fatigue life limit is normally higher than the first damage threshold and is rather linked to the second threshold, which corresponds to strong transverse cracks and local delaminations.

For short fibre composites the threshold for onset of fibre-matrix debonding is much lower than the measured fatigue limit. This can be shown by modelling the onset of debonding using simple Modified Coulomb criteria together with mean field homogenization methods. Use of average fibre stresses predicted by mean field homogenization methods yields upper limit of stress values for onset of damage, yet it was seen that the stresses at onset of debonding are significantly lower than the measured fatigue limit of such materials.

An extended and comprehensive description of the results in the present paper, including details of the experimental and numerical methodologies, is published in [21].

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